

A UWB EAGLE WING ANTIPODAL VIVALDI ANTENNA FOR UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLES JAMMING MISSION

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Abstract - This article presents a Vivaldi Antipodal Antenna with a semi-elliptical lateral radiator topology, similar to the wings of an eagle, called the Vivaldi Eagle Wing Antipodal Antenna. The tips formed by the Eagle Wing's cavities accumulate surface currents, making the surrounding air conductive, thus increasing the directivity of the electric field radiated by the antenna's main radiator. Another function of the radiating cavities is to improve the gain by reducing the strabismus by 4 degrees, reducing the cross-polarization commonly found in conventional Vivaldi Antipodal Antennas. An additional, this new topology will be to reduce the lower frequency limit to 1.535 GHz in order to operate anti-drone systems that use geolocation. The development and simulation of the antennas will be carried out using Ansys HFSS 2021 R1, allowing the optimization of the Eagle Wing cavities through the analysis of parameters such as S11, gain, near-field and far-field electric fields.

Keywords: UAV defense, Jamming technology, antipodal Vivaldi antenna, ultra-directive UWB.

INTRODUCTION

With the commercial diffusion of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV's), they began to become more accessible, reducing the cost of production and increasingly penetrating the civilian market. This growing access to this technology, coupled with technological advances, has raised concerns about the potential risks of the indiscriminate use of UAV's in civilian environments, leading to the establishment of stricter regulations regarding the use of UAV's [1] - [3]. The risks of using this technology are not only linked to acts of war such as the attempted assassination of Venezuelan President in 2018 [4], but also correlate with the invasion of privacy in urban environments [2], [3], [5]-[7]. With all the occasional risks of this technology, anti-UAV systems naturally need to be constantly evolving. In portable anti-UAV systems, at least two antennas are used to increase the effectiveness of interfering with the device's communication with the controller and operating in 0.433, 0.915, 2.400, 5.800 GHz and GNSS bands [2]. However, there is an ultra-wideband (UWB) antenna, the Vivaldi Antipodal Antenna (AVA) [8] - [10], which is easy to build because it is planar [9] - [14], and it is possible to improve its characteristics by modifying its topology [9]. These modifications help to improve the restrictions that this antenna has, such as the drainage of the gain in the main lobe (ML) to the side lobes (SL), and cross-polarization problems, which affect its signal directivity [9] and [15]. AVA optimization methods include the use of dielectric lenses [15], [16]-[27], metamaterial compositions [15], [17]-[19] and using radiating side cavities [9], [28] and [29]. Of all these methods, the latter is more efficient in improving the characteristics of the AVA, without increasing its construction complexity or changing the dimensions of the antenna [9], [28] and [29]. For portable anti-UAV systems, the use of an antenna that maintains or improves the interference results in the UAV's communication system is significant, reducing the weight of the equipment, as well as taking up less space to handle.

To meet this need, the proposed topology change will be based on lateral radiating cavities in the shape of semi-ellipses, resembling the wings of an eagle, and is called Eagle Wing (EW). The basis for this project was the ESE-AVA, available at [9]. Thus, the function of these lateral radiating cavities improves the gain characteristics, such as the strabismus to -1 degree and the expansion of the UWB low frequency limit (LFL) of the AVA to 1.535 GHz. Both improvements provided by this new topology are ideal for anti-UAV systems, as they help the antenna's directivity and the system's performance against drones equipped with a Global Positioning System (GPS) [30] - [32].

This paper is divided as follows: Section II - shows the new design; Section III - presents the results of the EW-AVA and AVA measurements; Section IV - demonstrates the use of the concept in anti-UAV operations; Section V - concludes the paper by presenting.

ANTENNA DESIGN

Fig. 1 (b) shows the AVA topology used in [9] and [15] to build the EW-AVA, based on the methodology of [33]. In this topology, the main radiator (endfire) and the rear radiator are made up of exponential curves, called $j_1(z)$ and $j_2(z)$, respectively. These exponential curves are parameterized by equations (1) - (3) [10].

$$j_i(z) = c_1 * e^{Rz} + c_2 \quad (1)$$

for $i \in \{1,2\}$,

$$c_1 = \frac{x_{i2} - x_{i1}}{e^{Rz_{i2}} - e^{Rz_{i1}}} \quad (2)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{x_{i2} * e^{Rz_{i2}} - x_{i1} * e^{Rz_{i1}}}{e^{Rz_{i2}} - e^{Rz_{i1}}} \quad (3)$$

Where, x_{i1} , z_{i1} , x_{i2} e z_{i2} , represent, respectively, coordinates (x, z) of H_{i1} and H_{i2} . While the value of the opening ratio (R) will depend on the value adopted for i , following equations (4) and (5).

$$i = 1 \Leftrightarrow R = 0,038 \quad (4)$$

$$i = 2 \Leftrightarrow R = 0,058 \quad (5)$$

However, this AVA has a small lower ground plane, constructed from a quarter of a circle of radius r_2 .

Fig. 1. Construction parameters of (a) EW-AVA; (b) AVA.

Based on the design proposed for the ESE-AVA [9], the EW-AVA is a Palm Tree class antenna [9] and [15], and its topology is shown in Fig. 1 (a). In order to improve the ML, reduce the SL and improve the S11 parameter by reducing the LFL, the topology uses radiating cavities in the shape of angled semi-ellipses, known as wings, arranged in a non-linear manner from a circle of radius r_1 . The tips formed by the wings aim to reduce the intense surface currents that are radiated by the sides of the conventional AVA [9], [15], [33] and [34].

As planar antennas can be scaled down or up by increasing and decreasing their dielectric constant, respectively [9], the parameters of the EW-AVA topology shown in Fig. 1 are shown in Table I.

TABLE I - EW-AVA and AVA topology parameters.

Topology Parameters			
a	32.85 mm	f	3.00 mm
b	14.29 mm	r ₁	46.00 mm
c	109.50 mm	r ₂	20.00 mm
d	3.10 mm	α	18.03 degrees
e	150.00 mm		

ANTENNA MEASUREMENTS

Using the Ansys HFSS 2021 R1 numerical analysis software, it was possible to analyze the parameters of the AVA with the EW-AVA, making it possible to optimize its design by improving the S11 parameter and gain. To carry out the numerical analysis, Ansys HFSS uses the Finite Element Method (FEM) [35] and [36], obtaining adequate accuracy for the design stage.

In order to compare the antennas built and modeled in the software, measurements were taken to obtain the S11 parameter curve and the polar radiation diagram.

To this end, using a Vector Network Analyzer (Lite VNA-64), the S11 parameter curves of the AVA and EW-AVA were obtained. Fig. 3 shows the S11 parameter curve, showing a reduction in the lower frequency limit from 2.178 GHz to 1.535 GHz. This increase in LFL is important for anti-UAV defense applications, considering that some are equipped with GPS which has an operating band between 1.563 and 1.587 GHz [30] - [32].

Fig. 3. Comparison of the measured and simulated S11 parameter of the EW-AVA and AVA.

In contrast, the radiation diagram was measured at a frequency of 2.450 GHz. This frequency was selected because it is widely used in commercial UAV communication, which operates from 2.400 to 2.483 GHz or 5.725 to 5.825 GHz [2], following the IEEE 802.11 communication protocol [37] - [39]. That said, to carry out the measurement, the transmitting antenna, EW-AVA, connected to a signal generator was positioned 1 m from the receiving antenna being analyzed, switching between AVA and EW-AVA. In this way, a signal analyzer connected to the receiving antenna captured gain values every 10 degrees, making it possible to draw the radiation diagram of the AVA and EW-AVA. With this data, it was possible to see that the new design improved the AVA's squint by 4 degrees and ML increased by 0.2 dB, improving the directivity of the design. Fig. 4 shows a comparison of the radiation diagram of the EW-AVA with that of the AVA.

Fig. 4. Radiation diagram of (a) EW-AVA; (b) AVA.

DEFENSE AGAINST UAVS

We set up an indoor test has been set up for the proof of concept (PoC) of using EAW-AVA for defense missions against UAV's, using jamming. Based on the test presented in [2], the aim of the PoC will be to obtain the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) from the spectral analysis of the signal from a UAV suffering from EW jamming [40]. A SNR can be calculated using equation (6) [40] and [41].

$$SNR [dBm] = S [dBm] - N [dBm] \quad (6)$$

Where S is the signal and N the noise.

In the PoC, a Fern-AVA was used, built from [33], connected to a spectrum analyzer to capture the interference that the EW-AVA signal causes in a UAV. To interfere with the UAV's communication with the controller, the EW-AVA was connected to a microwave signal generator, transmitting on the UAV's communication frequency, which is 2.417 GHz. The positioning of the EW was ensured by means of an electronic level meter, the L52 Cross Marking Level multifunction model from Miliseey. Tests were carried out at three distances between the UAV and the EW: 5, 10 and 15 m. An electronic tape measure, model LV 56 from LomVum & Miliseey, was used to determine the positioning of the antenna. To avoid interference from the environment, the UAV was placed in a semi-anechoic chamber made up of 24" x 12" x 4"H light blue absorber panels, model Slab Absorber from AEMI - A Microwave Vision Company, and a Styrofoam support was used to position the drone inside the chamber.

The PoC resulted in 3 curves, showing the interference caused by the antenna to the UAV at the 3 distances determined, whose drone lost communication with the controller in all the tests carried out, resulting in its engine being switched off.

Fig. 5 shows the curves obtained from the spectral analysis of the EW's interference with the UAV.

Fig. 5. Jamming performed by the EW-AVA at 5, 10, 15 m.

Using the data in Fig. 5 and considering that the S of the UAV is 40.00 dBm, the SNRs calculated were -4.57, 8.43 and 15.43 dBm for 5, 10 and 15 m, in that order. Thus, the test with the greatest interference was carried out at 5 m, resulting in an SNR of -4.47 dBm, which indicates that communication with the UAV was inhibited, since at least 40 dBm is required for video communication.

CONCLUSION

This research presented the EW-AVA, a new Palm Tree class topology for the AVA. With this new design, it was possible to increase the LFL by 0.643 GHz compared to the conventional AVA, allowing the antenna to combat UAV's equipped with GPS systems. Likewise, this design repaired the AVA's natural strabismus from -5 to -1 degrees, improving the antenna's directivity and target accuracy, an important factor in anti-UAV equipment. That said, the anti-UAV concept was a success, as it was able to generate noise that interfered with the UAV's communication with the controller. This was proven by the results calculated by SNR, these were -4.57, 8.43 and 15.43 dBm for 5, 10 and 15 m.

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